

Unravelling the mysteries of the amazing space and the creation of the universe!

**Space, interior space, greater space, and absolute space
(zero).**

**The Secret Biography of the Universe. From the Beginning to
the End of The Creation!**

***The background of the creation of the universe and all the
mysteries from the beginning to the end of the creation of the
universe are revealed here one by one. Cosmology and
Creationism have become one In this scientific theory!***

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Abstract:

To talk about space we have to talk about the universe, because space is a part of the universe. Again, in the context of the universe, naturally, it remains incomplete if we do not say something about its birth story. Therefore, in the discussion about space, the birth of the universe and its progress are also highlighted in this article.

Keywords:

Space, Universe, Cosmology, Creation theory, Metaverse, Virtual reality, Multiverse, Hypothesis, Scientific theory,

Introduction:

Different types of spaces exist at different levels. The space inside a particle and inside various objects can be called interior space. The space within the universe is what we call space. Again, the space of the original entity that the universe is inside can be called the greater space. Please see my creation theory to know about primordial beings or original entity and the birth of the universe. In my theory of creation, the infinite space beyond this original entity is called absolute space.

Space is not like a sheet or like a roof made of cloth. Space is a space that extends in many directions like the interior of a ball filled with air.

Chapter 1

The universe is developing bit by bit from a seed just like the seed of a plant. Just as the plant seed draws its supplies or food from soil, air and light for nourishment and growth, so the universe draws its supplies for its growth from the greater space of primordial being.

The universe is a living entity. If you can imagine your brain as big as the universe, it will look exactly like the universe. Just like the interior space of the universe, there is space within our brains.

The universe is actually a greatest brain. Within this brain there is also a mind, that mind is Visva-Mon or Cosmic Mind or God Mind.

The main quality, energy and power of the mind and brain is consciousness, as you have it. Consciousness exists all over the world. You or your mind and brain are a unit of this cosmic mind and brain.

Cosmic-Mind is the creator of all living beings and plants. It has created these in its body and mind elements.

This universe is not created by God, it is God itself. The Creator of the Universe as God is the primordial being~ Supreme Being.

From one point of view I saw so long. Now if we look at it from another point of view, it will be seen that this universe is an illusion. Like MetaVerse. It can be called virtual existence. The primordial being~ Supreme Being is the creator of this Maya world. Much like computer video games or animation movies.

Just as there is programming code behind the creation of an animation movie or video game, there is also a special cosmic

programming code behind it. To understand this better, please read Maharshi MahaManas' Theory of Creation.

Very briefly the gradual steps of the Creation:

1. The Original Being had created an almost similar mini image (copy) of it –from its own materials. →
2. The second (virtual) existence of the Original Being had been attained to a preconscious state through self-hypnotism (Yoga Nidra) and
It becomes like a fruit containing the seeds of many universe.→
3. After that, the fruit bursts with the first explosion and the seeds are scattered around it. These include the seeds of the Universe and the Anti-Universe. →
4. Those universe-seeds all began to develop simultaneously through the Big Bang. Like a tree from a seed, they gradually grow into many universes. →
5. God in the form of our universe existence is our creator.

From another point of view, both the past and the future of the universe exist. The future of the universe was determined from the moment it was born. When, where, exactly what will happen was created automatically at the time of the Big Bang. Cosmic events are like a pre-made film or video. If viewed from outside the universe, this video or film has both its past and future existence from somewhere in the middle of the film/ video.

Now let's turn our attention to the seemingly empty space within the universe called space.

All over the univers, a bubble like multidimensional, seemingly unobstructed or nearly unobstructed vacuum existence is called space.

This space existence came into existence as the universe was created through the great explosion. And as the universe progresses, this space is gradually expanding. It is an ever-expanding space that gradually inflates like a pumped-up ball.

This space is actually a special existence composed of invisible unperceived extraordinary particles of a particular frequency. These particles, like 'Stem cell', themselves grow at a rapid rate when needed. Science has not yet been able to discover them.

In general, this space is an invisible unfelt non-existent existence to us. That is why it is called a great vacuum.

Therefore, this space is not absolute zero. The primordial entity that exists outside the universe, beyond that primordial entity lies the Absolute Zero.

Our space is not empty at all. In addition to its own existence, it is filled with various cosmic rays, energies, particles and radiation and unknown objects and substances. It does not usually participate in various activities, including action-reaction, attraction and repulsion between those forces and particles. It is neutral idle indifferent.

Not only that everything in the universe is inhabited by space, also there is space inside everything.

As the universe was created, in addition to space, two more indivisible unique virtual existences were created. That is 'Time' and 'Destiny' (please see 'Time' and 'Destiny' articles). Some blend space and time together. But time and space are two distinct entities. The great relationship between time and space is that they are born from the same phenomenon.

Just like fish inside waters, so is our position in this space. There is space inside and outside, on all sides of us.

Some have described this unique space as different in their imagination. But none of them are the true form of this mysterious space. The space still remains intangible to us.

To understand the space, one has to move forward from the root, step by step. The original being (The original being or primordial being, from which the universe originated) is situated in absolute zero. And within it the space with the universe was born (see my latest cosmogony). At the beginning of my cosmogony, there is a brief description of the absolute zero. The description is as follows:

Absolute zero! The rootless endless formless actual zero. Not our known space. Beyond the area of the universe, beyond the territory of the original being. The everlasting vacuum that exists, that absolute zero!

Silent waveless indifferent a non-existent existence. Within that unchanged indestructible steadfast zero, unable to access any moving material or energy from here.

The original being is situated in that absolute zero. And the great creation was born in that original being. This great creation is made up of a large number of universes. One of them is our universe.

In my cosmogony, there is a description of the original being as follows:

Original being lies at a certain limit in the middle of that absolute zero. The original being is mainly composed of the original particles, the absolute particles, and the original energies. It is also full of numerous joint particles and radiation, with the absolute conscious-mind (in philosophy).

The pre-great-creation like a fruit made up of many universe seeds is created through first explosion. And, at one time, there was a great explosion in the universe-seeds of this fruit like pre-superstructure. From which sprouted up the universes are evolving like countless trees.

Different elemental particles and energies with different frequencies are created from original particle's different levels of vibration. There are different type of programming codes (nearly similar to the computer programming code language) at the core of the component of original particles and elementary particles.

It is important to mention here that the original particle has no 'dimension'. The original particle is a virtual entity, created by that type of programming code or at the root of which is the special programming code.

Different particles of different frequencies created from the original particles are actually the embodiment of the latent programming code.

Eventually, when this cosmic collapse will take place, as soon as the space is destroyed.

My theory about space is ~ This gradually expanding seemingly empty space is not empty at all. Space is an incomparable existence, made of inexperienced special particles of a particular

frequency. Particles that are capable of growing themselves by the birth of new particles, such as the cell division process. Let's name these space particles~ 'MahaManas' particles.

In this context, let's talk about the 'O~M' sound from the dynamic universe. O-U-M is the basic sound of the universe!

Scientists have managed to record the sounds of the universe, This news has just been published.

A long time ago in one of Maharshi MahaManas' articles published on SpeakingTree website, he said,

O-U-M is the basic sound of the universe!

A long time ago in one of my articles published on SpeakingTree website, I said, 'O-U-M' is actually the basic sound of the universe. The vibration and rotation is going on all over the universe. From there the 'O-M' or 'O-U-M' is always being produced.

Since there is no air in the universe, that sound does not reach our ears. But it is possible to record that sound by suitable mechanical means. Just as a motor makes a hum like 'O-M' or 'O-U-M' when it moves or spins, so does the 'O-U-M' sound from the moving and vibrating universe.

Reference:

To understand better, I request you to read this research papers "What Exactly Destiny Is" by Maharshi MahaManas. And Unveiling the truth of 'Time' and 'Time travel' along the path of science.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360738812_What_exactly_Destiny_is_an_exploration_from_a_scientific_viewpoint

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357083188_Unveiling_the_truth_of_'Time'_and_'Time_travel'_along_the_path_of_science

Chapter 2

UNRAVELLING THE MYSTERY OF THE CREATION OF THE UNIVERSE!

The Secret Biography of the Universe. From the Beginning to the End of The Creation!

The background of the creation of the universe and all the mysteries from the beginning to the end of the creation of the universe are revealed here one by one. Cosmology and Creationism have become one In this scientific theory!

Abstract :

This theory scientifically shows that the universe is our creator and it has a mind and consciousness. The universe is actually nothing but a gigantic brain. It created us with its body, mind and consciousness. This theory explained with logic that there is a progressively developing supremely conscious mind within this universe. No external sentient being or God created this universe, it is God itself (if it is called God). God is only the creator of various creatures and plants. The presence of a highly intelligent mind behind all these creations will be proved later in the detailed discussion.

Besides, this cosmic entity or God is not the controller of all worldly events, but everything is happening in a predetermined order by the automatic worldly system called 'Destiny'. Even God in the form of Universe is subject to Destiny. This system called Destiny originated at the moment of birth of this universe through the Big Bang.

Just as there is a programming language behind all the information in the computer, such as text, image, audio video etcetera, and all programming language is based on the notation of special combinations of binary codes, Similarly, behind everything in this universe there is a programming language, and at its core is the notation of original particles. There are also binary systems.

Just as music is a melodic design of different combinations of tones of different frequencies, so also in cosmic music there is a play of different frequencies and combinations of tones of original particles. At the root of everything there is a sound or tone produced from original particles of different frequencies. Different combinations of tones of different frequencies create different energies, forces, matter, antimatter and many things.

This theory can be called 'The Theory of Everything'.

Almost all my theories have gradually manifested themselves in the way of logic and science. From the point of view of logic and science the background of the creation of the universe and all the mysteries from the beginning to the end of the creation of the universe are revealed here one by one.

Why, for what purpose and under what circumstances this creation began, how it began, and how this creation proceeds towards its goal, and what is its end, step by step the mystery of each chapter is revealed in this great cosmology. The main point of cosmology or creation theory is that the original being played with itself. It is

nothing but a leisure game for it to make and break and decorate itself in various forms. I am discussing this in detail later.

Keywords :

New cosmology, new creation theory, new creationism, mystery of creation, cosmic mind, new doctrine, behind the creation, mystery of destiny, mystery of time,

Introduction:

We have observed unusual behavior of photons and electrons during various experiments in physics and quantum physics. Looking at them they are behaving one way, but not looking at them they are behaving differently! This test proves that they have consciousness. This is a great proof of the existence of mind and consciousness of the universe existence. We will continue to find more and more evidence of the cosmic mind and its intelligence.

Consciousness is present in every particle, in every unit of this universe-shaped ocean of consciousness. Because our consciousness is so low, we are unable to perceive it. Consciousness has to be realized with higher consciousness, and mind has to be realized with higher conscious mind.

Consciousness is the main quality or characteristic of 'mind' software. If there is consciousness there will be mind. That 'mind' may be the 'mind' of lower consciousness, or the 'mind' of higher consciousness. Whether it is a small-sized mind of low power or a large-sized high-powered mind, it is actually a mind.

If our brain is magnified many times over, it will look like the universe. Just as there is a conscious entity in the form of 'mind'

software within our brain, so there is a mind in the universe. It is the world-mind or cosmic mind. This universe mind is our creator. There is no such thing as creator outside of it. The creator has created the living being and human being from its body material and its mind.

We do everything according to this mind-software and the programming language embedded in it, created by the Creator. If the Creator wanted us to worship it according to certain rules, and if it wanted to guide us to a certain religious path, then naturally it would have included such a program in our mind. It did not need to compose different types of scriptures in different places for it. In fact, these are the manipulations of religious traders.

If we imagine this universe form the Creator as an ocean, we are just a few drops of water in it. To know this ocean, first of all we have to gain knowledge about its few drops of water. The more accurately we know ourselves and our surroundings, The more we know the (universe formed) Creator. Creator did not create this universe, this universe itself is the Creator. Nothing exists outside of this universe except an imaginary creator.

There is a mind within the universal body of the creator. That is the Cosmic Mind. That great artist~ the cosmic-mind has created innumerable living beings and plants one after the other with its own body and mind material.

This univers-nature is our creator. This cosmic 'body' and this cosmic 'mind' together constitute the existence of the Creator. The universe and our Creator are actually the same. Our Creator is not a fairy tale hero.

This universe is not created by our creator or God, it is the creator itself. Nothing exists in this universe apart from God. Except only the dormant or latent original being (discussed in detail in my cosmology). Only parts of it—like living things—plants etc. have been created by

the Creator. Although the creator created them from its own body material. Our mind is also created—from the Visva-Mind or Cosmic Mind. Nothing was created from nothing. Nothing is created by itself. We are all part of the Creator, part of the universe.

This universe-existence is our creator. That which is created from the original entity or Paramatma. This original entity is not directly our creator, and has no special role in this worldly activity. In this world-activity the original entity is like a silent indifferent and latent spectator. Original being~ Paramatma is not self-contained or complete. Perfection is the state of complete stillness, full static~ idle state. No creation is possible from perfection. In that full state there is nothing to want, nothing to get. Because of that there is nothing to do. There is no question of creation.

Even the original entity is not complete. It also has some needs~ some lacks. It does not know who it is, why it is, and whence it comes or originates. It doesn't know what its end will be. Its desire to know itself is the original cause of creation.

Necessarily, that original being~ voluntarily lost itself to find itself (self-search) again~ this is the secret of creation and the Cosmic life journey. This is discussed in detail in my Modern Cosmology 'Maha Sristitatwa'.

There are many proofs of our Creator's intelligence scattered around the world. When we can perceive it as a conscious being, all those proofs will continue to appear before our eyes one after the other. And, if we recognize the gradually developing World-Mind or Cosmic Mind as our Creator, and if we understand its developing (biological) artworks which has been developed according to its development of consciousness, then conventional evolutionism will become futile.

Cosmic Mind that is God-Mind is the Creator of living things and plants

The entire universe including all organisms, is made up of programming languages like computer programming languages. And there is a programmer behind the creation of all living beings. The universe existence with a highest conscious cosmic mind itself is that Creator.

Behind everything there is a constantly developing highest intelligent conscious mind. Many problems can be solved only by realizing it.

'Mind' is nothing but a highly developed software. The Mind of an organism is organic software. Mind is a very high quality software powered by programming language, much like computer software. Like computer software, 'Mind' software is powered by a variety of instructional programming languages. This Mind software works through the bio-hardware, processor, nervous system and bio-electricity called the brain. Mind software is many times better than ordinary computer software. There is consciousness and intelligence in the 'Mind' software. The 'Mind' software is also capable of programming itself and being programmed by others. There is also a developer or programmer behind this software. Nothing is created by chance. Cosmic mind software is many times more advanced and powerful than human 'Mind' software.

There are many evidences of the existence of that highest intelligent mind scattered inside and outside of us, just need to have a sufficiently developed conscious mind to realize it. But that is not the God of conventional ideas or the God of religion.

Many are skeptical of the cosmic mind. For those who have not yet fully understood or known their own mind, it is really difficult to understand or know the existence of cosmic-mind, to realize its existence. The mind has to be understood with the mind. And it requires observant~ conscious~ truthful, sufficiently developed blind-faith-free-mind.

I think these very simple evidences would be very helpful in understanding the existence of the cosmic-mind:

Its intelligence is reflected in the strategies it has devised for the purpose of maintaining their existence and lineage through the reproduction of mortal organisms. And, intelligence is the sign of the presence of 'Mind'. That is, where there is intellect, there must be mind.

Let's talk about that strategy: the strategy of arranging sexual pleasure in the organism and by tempting the organism towards sexual pleasure, by incorporating the programming language of sexual intercourse in the organism, to motivate or compel the organism to have sexual intercourse must be a sign of its intelligence.

Another manifestation of the Creator's intelligence is the creation of female and male creatures for the purpose of creating better living beings and their proper body-organs and affectionate mind towards child. Behind all this there is clearly the existence of intelligence or intelligent conscious mind.

In addition, so that we do not destroy our own bodies, we try to avoid diseases, injuries and attacks, the Creator has included in us such instructions in the form of programming languages of Pain Feeling or suffering.

Although not all of its functions are complete and flawless, for many of us it is not satisfactory enough. Yet at the time of creation (at a particular stage of development of consciousness) it has done a lot on the basis of its knowledge and consciousness. The Creator has also given us a lot of self-defense.

Ever since the birth of the universe, it has been moving from a very early state of consciousness towards full consciousness, following the path of development of consciousness. The development of knowledge,

experience and consciousness is observed through the creation of new creatures, one after the other.

Although it cannot be called benevolent or absolute benefactor of living beings. The creature is nothing more than a toy or play dolls in its playroom. If it were for the welfare of all living beings, it would not make one living being the food of another living being.

If you search, you will find many more such evidence. And if we observe a little more closely, we will see that it has devised various strategies for the purpose of making us fully developed human beings, from a very low consciousness to a high and higher consciousness.

Also, a closer look reveals that the cosmic mind has been developing little by little over a long period of time. The improvement in its creativity along with the development of the mind can be clearly seen by looking at the development (From worms to advanced humans) of its developing organism.

The mind is behind the creation of everything. Our Creator Cosmic Mind did not create this universe, it is the universe itself. There is also a Creator and the mystery of creation behind it. This has been described in detail in my cosmology or creation theory. In this science based theory we see that the cosmic-mind that is the nature has created only plants and organisms.

fig- 1

Pre-creation phase :

Absolute zero! Without beginning and without end~ formless~ actual zero! Space as we know it is not. beyond the area of the universe—the infinite space that exists beyond the realm of original being, —is the Absolute Void. Quiet~ neutral~ waveless~ silent~ unruffled~ A non-existent existence. Zero existence! Unchangeable—Indestructible— Immoveable In that void no moving matter or energy can enter from here.

Within that absolute void, the original being (Paramatma) occupies a certain area. Before this creation, it was in a deep sleep at the end of the previous creation. Later this great creation was born in that original being. Its creation consists of many universes. One of them is our universe.

The original entity is essentially the original particle — the ultimate particle — a Supreme Mind existence composed of primordial energy and consciousness. It is also full of numerous coupled particles and radiation. In association with them are many other objects~ non objects,

—primary matter, antimatter, and primitive energy. Which are impossible to express in our language.

Before creation—in the very beginning, a kind of primordial particle was present. Two primordial particles are created from it. One is the 'X' primordial particle with positive charge, and special frequency with '1' programming language and '1' dimension. And the other is 'Y' original particle~ negative charged with special frequency and '0' (zero) programming language and zero dimension or dimensionless. Different elementary particles are formed by combining different numbers of 'X' and 'Y' primordial particles. Multiple primordial particles combine in special combinations to create different energy and different elementary matter particles.

Every primordial particle and elementary particle has its own special programming language built into it. The universe and everything in it~ is the embodiment of the underlying programming language. A primordial particle with different degrees of spin and frequency and charge - combines with other primordial particles to create elementary matter and energy of different character. Behind these variations lie different programming languages— the presence of particular combinations of different numbers of primitive particles.

From the primordial particles to the elementary particles to all matter particles and energy particles and their special combinations of various worldly existences, there is a variety of 'programming language' embedded in everything. Somewhat similar to our computer programming language code. From the primordial particle to the later created particles of different frequencies, all forms of mundane

existence— manifested or embodied forms of various unmanifest or latent programming languages.

As a result of various types of addition-subtraction, exchange, acceptance-exclusion, etc. behavior, new and many types of particles and entities are created. Like- XY, XYY, XXX, YYY, (XY)+(XYY), (XXY)+(XYY) etc. with different mass and massless, with different charge and without charge, zero dimension to multi dimensional existence.

Space, matter, energy, consciousness etc. are created. Within the fundamental particles lies latent all potential for further transformation. These particles are transformable and sometimes have contrasting qualities. Various additions and subtractions between primitive particles also result in inverse and partially inverse particles. As a result of a special arrangement of the basic particles and the various particles created from them, the primordial entity with primordial mind and primordial consciousness—'Paramatma'—is created.

Therefore, this original entity is not fully conscious or full of consciousness. And, the original being - 'Paramatma' is not complete in all aspects. Perfection is absolute deadlock or stalemate. Totally passive — qualityless state, which is synonymous with unconsciousness. From which no creation can arise. Fully static condition~ a fully conscious being has nothing to desire. There is nothing to gain. So, it has nothing to do. If one is self-complete, there is no question of creating anything. Where there is no goal, no purpose, no movement - creation is impossible.

No, the original being—the 'Paramatma' is not full, but almost full. With regard to our lower consciousness ~ although it appears to be complete in appearance, in real sense it is only called Supreme consciousness 'Paramatma'. Nothing else exists here except the Supreme Soul 'Paramatma' alone.

There is the tiniest degree of imperfection in it. There is very slow and subtle activity. Although its exterior seems almost waveless, there is an undercurrent of excitement.

In reality, there is no such thing as a fully paused and fully active state. Even in maximal rest or inactive states there is some activity, albeit very little. The reverse is also true. Action resumes from a state of rest, like awakening from sleep.

Once upon a time the sleep of the original being~ Supreme Soul ended. It is as if the morning of the absolute time (it is not the time of the universe) has come. With the cessation of sleep, like ours, various needs—various desires are awakened, like—desire for action, desire for happiness and pleasure, desire for fulfillment—which operate subconsciously in the common people, subject to their consciousness—desire to be different and to do many things, and desire to have many things. Desire for companionship arises—to relieve loneliness and to achieve fulfillment. Such a desire to satisfy the imperfect needs of the almost unconscious mind, — that if I get him or that thing I will be happy — I will be fulfilled. My loneliness will disappear. Because it is not possible to achieve perfection and immortality in one life, and at the same time, the desire to have a child arises from the motive of alleviating loneliness. The desire or need for food arises for the sake of sustaining life and enjoying the happiness of tongue. Later, when self-awareness is awakened, the desire for self-knowledge and self-development is awakened one by one after the end of sleep.

At the end of the sleep of original being (Paramatma), almost similar needs and desires arose. Just as our desires are manifestations of the various needs of the mind and body, so are the manifestations of the original being (Paramatma). Behind that need there are various actions-reactions inside its mind and body.

At the end of sleep, from these thoughts, heat-pressure-excitement and activity increase gradually in the inner body center of Paramatma. There, the original particles and conjugated particles are mixed together, breaking up and creating new particles - new substances. Gradually the preparation for making creation-seed for the great creation continue inside its body.

The Supreme Soul~ original entity, thinking and understanding its own condition, without seeing any other way, necessarily, eventually invents a beautiful way to meet its needs. First it creates (via programming language)— a miniature virtual existence similar to itself—within itself. Then, according to the command or will of the Original Being, its second entity~ through self-hypnotic suggestion it becomes concentrated into seed form through deep yoga sleep (hypnotic sleep). By this way it transforms its own form-quality-consciousness, knowledge-power-ability etc. into seed form. It brings itself down to the pre-infantile level of unconsciousness, losing itself to engage in the game of self-enquiry or self-discovery.

The Creation activities are nothing but a pleasure game of losing oneself willfully and finding oneself again.

fig- 2

The journey of creation has begun!

Then, that Maya entity that is illusory existence / second existence of the original being ('Paramatma') gradually shrinks itself and becomes spherically concentrated at one point—the center of the 'Paramatma'.

Then, at a particular stage of contraction, an explosion takes place within the fruit as a aggregation of many world-seeds, due to the inconceivable heat-pressure and density at the center of the Original being.

First explosion! Through that explosion, the fruit burst and many world-seeds were created. From the center of the Original being, those world-seeds come out with great speed in all directions. That fruit

consist of equal number of world-seeds and world-seeds of opposite qualities. If seeds of opposite qualities meet each other, both will be destroyed. They are opposite world-seeds i.e. seeds of opposite universe.

The primordial explosion took place in the Creation fruit containing the seeds of many universes!

fig- 3

Then at some point, every world-seed had a Big bang, almost at the same time. Immediately germinating~ blossoming, undergoing cell-division to gradually become the universe, they began the journey of self-development.

Each continued to expand into multiple universes through continuous explosions! Innumerable explosions are happening inside them. Breaking and joining, change, transformation, new creation and destruction, countless strange events. All these things are happening in these universes in the cycle of creation - equilibrium - motion -

destruction. The newborn worlds are moving away from their explosion center, and each world is expanding from its respective center. When the expanding worlds come into contact with the nearest opposite world, then all creation, including both worlds, will be destroyed.

And that Original being — the 'Paramatma' sitting in the seat of the audience watching alone, silently enjoying — this creation that happens automatically one after the other like a movie.

Meanwhile let's see what these poor newborns are doing! They are almost unconsciously moving forward step by step from helpless childhood to full development. One of these evolving worlds is our universe! A very small part of it is our green planet~ Earth.

By continuing in this way - from budding through cell-division, little by little along the path of development, they will finally achieve full self-development!

Through the software within the primordial seed-cell – a series of events will take place one after the other based on the plan of future activities in-built within it in the form of 'programming language'.

However, this programming language contains the original desires, such as self-discovery, self-realization, self-development, etc., but it does not specify in detail what will happen, when-where-by whom, and how. Then the joy of playing is not there! All this happens automatically by destiny (discussed in detail about destiny in the article 'What exactly destiny is').

Various events are taking place one after the other at different levels of development. Various changes - transformations, as well as the gradual development of knowledge, experience and consciousness.

Creation has begun, — its progress is going on. Let's take a peek inside the mind of Original being at this leisure.

The Original Being awoke at the end of its sleep, resumed its work as on previous mornings. It knows there is nothing to gain—nothing to do. Somehow life is going on.

Not that it doesn't have anything to ask for. But there is no hope of getting them. So it put all its needs to sleep. But what happened to that, the worm of that need is eating original being's inside. It makes it uncomfortable sometimes. Sometimes restless - excited - dissatisfied - depressed - makes it a bit angry. But all these are very gentle emotions. Never become excessive. Therefore, from the outside, it appears to be a self-contained, fully conscious, silent being. As if it is absorbed in itself. Tranquil— engrossed— peaceful, Radiant Glorious Absolute Being, The form of perfection!

But what is the shortage, what is the demand, which has kept it active even today! For which, to forget the disappointment, to enjoy the heat of excitement, to kill the coolness of boredom, and sometimes to relieve the excitement,—it had to arrange the game of creation again and again by itself. Why, for what—?

Before going into this topic, let us see how much of its ability - inability, knowing - unknown, desire - unwillingness can be found.

It can do as much as he wants. Can, — but it's limited to its region or body. Its body and mind are very much under its control. It is aware of everything that is happening in the body and mind. But it is unable to go anywhere else in the absolute void. Unable to move from its place. It cannot do whatever it likes with its own body. Cannot shrink or expand its size, or double or multiply itself. And because it can't, it creates a small illusory version of its own, through which it fulfills its wishes again and again. All these desires of its but largely depend on

its body and mind. Even if the body is made of different materials or other materials, it is still a body with consciousness

Like ours, its desires arise based on action-reaction and cause-and-effect. Its will is not created arbitrarily. Its desire arises out of its physical-mental composition, environment and time, and perhaps under the influence of voluntary or involuntary unknown forces.

It knows about its powers. It knows, it is unable to go anywhere. It knows that it has neither decay nor growth. But it does not know, the secret of its birth! It knows nothing about its beginning and end, birth and death. As if it has no beginning— no end, —it goes on like this—it goes on. The question arises in its mind, is it created from this absolute zero?! Is the secret of the creation of the original being hidden in the absolute void?!

Sometimes the question arises, who - it, from where - how it came or originated, what is the purpose of its life! What is the consequence! Where the beginning — where the end of this absolute zero! Who is its creator! Does it have any friend somewhere or not, these questions arise in its mind.

It does not know what is elsewhere in the absolute void, what is happening. All it knows is that no light, wave, energy, radiation, or anything known to it can travel through absolute void. There the sight does not extend — endless darkness.

Original being knows not to get anything from anyone, nor to give anything to anyone. —In spite of all this it has no indolence, for it has within it the strongest vital force—the supreme vitality. There is a strong desire to work - great enthusiasm. For which it is ever so active — alive!

For the time being, without thinking about the past and the future, surrendering itself to the hands of the unknown destiny - being Immersed in the happening present it is enjoying its life in ecstasy.

It is enjoying the game like a happy child. As always, when the game is over, it—the original entity—the Paramatma, will surrender itself to the lap of sleep in absolute peace like a naughty child.

And Vishwatma — Vishwatma or God here means our world-existence. In this universe-existence there is a mind—the world-mind or cosmic-mind. Here the word 'God' is used for ease of understanding. We will call it 'Vishwatma'.

There is also a world-mind in the opposite world nearest to our world. Our world—the world in which I speak, you hear. Or I'm writing, you're reading. Even in the opposite world you are - I am. Everything that is here, everything that is happening — everything is there and is happening there. Although this world has no direct connection with that world, there is an invisible inner pull.

Although composed of opposite particles, everything in that world is the same as this world. 'You' and 'I' there are not opposite qualities and characters compared to here. Their opposite quality can be understood only when the 'you' here and the 'you' there or both worlds meet each other directly. As soon as they meet, both worlds including both 'you' will be destroyed immediately. Again, although they have opposite qualities, they are strongly attracted to each other.

Now let us turn our attention to Vishwatma (God). Maha Vishwa the great universe form Body, universe-Mind, Vishwa-Shakti or world power. The entire Universal Being is real God (Vishwatma). It has a body, a mind, various desires, various activities. It has acquired most of its attributes, power, will-dislike, desire, knowledge-consciousness, etc., from the Original being— by birth. But all that lies dormant, — waiting to develop.

The universe-body is not only this earth, but a star-world like the solar system consisting of many planets, small and large like the earth, satellites and numerous asteroids and one or more stars. A constellation with billions of such star-worlds. And this universe or God's body with millions of such constellations. How many strange things are in this body! Starting from primordial particles - atoms - superatoms, comets, novae, super-novae, black-holes, dark-matter, dark-energy antimatter etc. are many things. There are many different beings, different kinds of sentient beings - creatures, plants and many more different things.

Space: A bubble-like multidimensional, seemingly free and empty existence throughout the world is called space. As soon as the universe was created through the big bang, our space was created. And this space is gradually expanding along with the universe. This space is actually a kind of invisible Insensible a special existence made up of particles of special frequencies. As in the process of cell division, these particles multiply themselves as necessary. Science has not yet been able to discover it.

In general, this space is an invisible and imperceptible existence to us. Hence it is called space. So, this space is not absolute zero. The Absolute Void is beyond the Creation in which the collective universe of many universes resides—even beyond Original existence.

This space of ours is not empty at all. Apart from its own existence, it is filled with various cosmic rays—energy, particles and radiation. It usually does not participate in various activities including action-reaction, attraction-repulsion between those forces and particles. It is neutral—passive— stoical. Not only that everything in the world is situated in space, but also space exists within everything. Space contains nothing—neither excludes.

As soon as the universe was created - apart from space, two other Ineffable imperceptible distinct virtual existences were created. They are 'Time' and 'Destiny' (see separate article on Time and Destiny). Some confuse space and time. But time and space are two separate entities. The great connection between time and space is that they are simultaneously born from the same event.

Much like the fish in the water of the pond, so is our position in this space. Space is all around us—inside and outside. This ethereal space has been described by some in various forms as per their conception or imagination. But none of those imaginations are the real shape or form of this mysterious space. Space still remains remains out of reach to us.

To understand space, one has to proceed step by step from the very core. The location of the Original entity in the absolute void. And within that Original being, many universes with many spaces as the great creation were born. The space between the universes is called - outer space.

At the beginning of my creation theory aka cosmology I have given a brief description about absolute zero. Within that absolute void there is the location of the original being. And within that original being, great creation was born. This creation consists of many universes. One of them is our universe.

The primordial explosion created the fruit-like pre-creation containing the seeds of many universes. And, once the big bang(s) took place in the cosmic seeds inside that fruit. From those world-seeds the universes are gradually growing like innumerable trees.

We have observed a little earlier the birth of God in the form of the universe. Now I see, like us, he also has childhood, adolescence, youth etc. There is a gradual progression towards the end. Vishwatma or

God mind is also developing gradually. Its life-course is progressing step by step through increasing awareness from incomplete knowledge and consciousness to the goal of full knowledge and consciousness.

It started its journey from the darkness of ignorance, walking step by step like a child. As it goes on, it is getting rid of its ignorance, delusion and blindness. Gradually its life is becoming illuminated with the light of new consciousness.

A very early childhood was spent in utter ignorance, impetuous~growing at fast speed. Childhood is also spent in an almost unconscious state, running around playing, acting as it pleases, carelessly - driven by inner urges. Even with some awareness in adolescence, with infatuation, ignorance-blindness, blind-passion — lust-ridden with eccentricity — have come a long way. Due to the simultaneous presence of two active minds (conscious and subconscious mind) of two different consciousness-levels at the same time, just as there is a contradiction between us, so it has happened in Vishwatma or God.

As it progresses in this way, it begins to understand itself little by little as its consciousness increases. God in the form of universe gradually becomes aware of its powers, abilities, actions, goals—objectives. So far it has been playing aimlessly without realizing it. Now it is time to walk consciously. At different times, according to the increasing level of consciousness, the changed attitude, desires of the time, it plays with different objectives. Playing with itself~ the game of creation.

Although seemingly aimless, it is unconsciously moving forward according to pre-programming. Another thing to remember is that we are created by it in its body and mind elements at a certain level of consciousness, so it has a lot in common with us. Another thing, even though it is called 'God' for ease of understanding, there is a lot of difference between this God as universe and the conventional concept of 'God'.

Self-enquiry arises as soon as enough consciousness is gained. It became busy searching for its answer. The former sport slowly came to a halt. Begins to achieve its noble goal~ self-discovery. A new game begins to progress towards perfection, with the goal of ever-faster development.

As consciousness grows gradually, he begins to gain self-knowledge little by little. Gradually many things become clear. He becomes mature gradually.

Who am I—, why—, where I came from—, where I will go—, for what purpose I was created—(?) This question is not new today. This question has been resonating in the hearts of all of you, knowingly or unknowingly - since the dawn of creation.

These questions are the root cause of creation. As I am asking myself, 'Who am I - why - from where - to where', the universe (God) is also asking these same questions. Again, the original entity - Paramatma is also wounding itself with these questions like arrows!

The purpose of this great life is to go out in search of the roots with self-inquiry (although it does not know if it will get the answer to this question at all). This is what many people call 'Creation Activity'.

In fact, this creation is nothing more than a fantasy of Original being. All this is the creation of its mind. As such, God in form of universe can also be called its mind-born child.

All the desires which the Original being has been unable to fulfill in its own life, this creation is for the purpose of fulfilling all those desires through imagination.

God is not only for the self-seeking, and not for the search for its Creator, but another search continues within it knowingly or

unknowingly, that is the search for its friend. Suffering from the pangs of loneliness, plagued by desires, then God decides in its heart, 'Yes, my main aim is to know myself. But it also has to be seen with that, am I alone here or I have a friend somewhere around.

But how will it be possible! It is only capable of expanding itself. As a result of the expansion of this great creation consisting of many worlds, it is not possible for God (universe) to go anywhere else in the body or region of the Original Being except by spreading and move on along the prescribed path.

Necessarily it splits into billions of parts like a burning fireball with renewed vigor, spreading out in all directions with great speed—it goes forth for the purpose of conquering the ten directions. Like a fireworks display across space in celebration of winning a kingdom. Sometimes a chunk is broken into many small pieces, and sometimes many pieces are combined to form a big chunk or planet or star.

Stretching itself forward with unstoppable rapidity. It has no time to look back. Through one burst after another, through cell-division at a compound rate—going on constantly.

It repeatedly builds and breaks itself out of its own material at various levels of developing consciousness. And it decorates itself in various ways with the colors of its imagination.

Its creative artist-mind is always active to relieve the monotony of the journey, to keep itself cheerful, and to relieve the stress of work in various ways.

Although there are many friendly worlds in the great creation of multiverse, at first our universe knew nothing about them. Having progressed a lot along the evolutionary path, it eventually found its closest friend.

To make the original desire successful, to get pleasure - endless thinking is going on. It wants quick success, wants to get rid of monotony, it wants variety, and wants pleasure. The artist is in pursuit of new creations. Also in the desire to gain perfection.

Through constant research it is discovering itself in ever-new forms—in many ways. It is the creator, it is also the creation. The artist-researcher, engrossed in the joy of creation, has come a long way and now it has become mature.

Almost crazy with the joy of great creation~ the Infatuated Viswatma (God) possessed with immense happiness~ what else would it create, all the knowledge, consciousness, creation and discovery was in the form of seeds. As time goes on, development takes place step by step through various events. That what is happening is predestined to happen.

This is called luck! No, there is no directly controlling person or conscious entity directly behind it. All this is not happening at the whim of anyone. Everything that is happening in the universe is happening through the combination of two different forces, voluntary and involuntary. Voluntary energy is working according to the instructions or 'program' or 'pre-program' embedded in the original seed-cell and all world-cells. And, the involuntary energy operates almost automatically, following the law of cause-effect, action-reaction in the flow of events.

Everything that is happening here, has happened and will happen, has its root cause in that big bang moment. That's called luck or fate or destiny. God itself is bound by this fate or destiny. We are only part of it. About Fate or Destiny has been discussed in detail in a separate chapter at the end.

Vishwatma's (God's) will-dislikes and our will-dislikes all these arise predestinedly. Our will is not our own, it also awakens at

predetermined times and fades away at predetermined times. That pre-programmed' voluntary force and predetermined the involuntary force called 'destiny' created by the Big Bang, have been working together all along. Destiny is created mainly from involuntary power! And, from the willful power came the world-mind or God-mind and our mind. This mind and its will—thoughts—are also subject to that involuntary power. This mind is developing little by little in keeping with destiny or sequence of events. The original source of volition power is the Original Being.

What forms the universe would take at different times, as well as the existence of living beings and other sentient beings and their various states were all preplanned in the form of a 'program' within the world-seed. That 'program' exists in every cell of us and even all living things, including all cosmic matter-particles born from that Original being.

In the unison of that volitional action in 'program' form and involuntary action in the form of destiny, the cosmic melody continues to be composed.

This is a strange finding. At the beginning of this search, up to a large part, who is searching, whom is searching, why is searching, where is searching~ all this remains unknown. Yet the search goes on without knowing it—on and on. For so long this movement~ this spreading was involuntarily~ unconsciously. Now that movement—that spread—is refreshed—, with new vigor—intentionally—consciously.

This is the primordial purpose behind the development of consciousness of humans and various forms of conscious entity on earth and other planets. Billions of us, knowingly or unknowingly, are running towards that self-inquiry~ that primal question, as part of the universe/God.

A very rapid expansion at a very high speed within a few moments would seem like an explosion.

fig- 4

The secret of cosmology and creationism!

Vishwatma (or God or Creator) and the entire universe, including the living world created by it, is an illusory existence. It is a pre-planned drama like a giant video game or hologram drama created and operated by high quality programming language, much like a computer program.

Our intelligence, which we know as natural, is actually artificial intelligence created by our creator.

Just as we ourselves being an illusory existence, create illusory worlds with many illusory characters in computer games, so Vishwatma (or

God) itself, being an illusory existence, created the so-called real world that we can experience with this living world.

Just as man has been created by the Vishwatma or God, so also by man and by the highly advanced beings or advanced conscious entities of other planets and other worlds, illusory worlds and creatures or living-like animated illusory characters or entities have been and are being created.

The Episode of Creature Creation

That big bang! — That fireworks display across space is a distant memory today. Just work and work—no time to look back. Yet in the midst of it sometimes he becomes absent-minded for a moment, — sinks into the pit of memory.

Primordial Life — The creation of unicellular organisms and proto-plants is rooted in the creation of the universe. In that Big Bang and the many subsequent explosions, the basic elements of the early living cells and early plant cells were created and spread throughout the universe. Later, they undergo various transformations, through a complex chemical process, slowly combining and transforming to form the seeds of primitive organisms and primitive plant cells. Much later, in various parts of the universe-body of God— being getting favorable environmental conditions for growth, they gradually proliferate through cell division.

Beyond very childhood, with a little age ~ with a little knowledge, God becomes aware of them. The child-God observed with amazement, what a great number of very low-consciousness creatures of various kinds had been created in the various parts of its world-body.

The strange shape, odd behavior of these tiny-bodied, low-consciousness creatures fascinate it. It also noticed that in various

parts of its vast body, countless microscopic micro-plants of various kinds had arisen by themselves.

The inquisitive mind of the child-god became very excited and interested in all these primitive creatures and primitive plants. In the first state, organisms and plants were not created by anyone's conscious will. Primitive organisms and primordial plants are the spontaneous creation, inevitable result of the great creative process through environmental conditions and events.

In other words, all these were in the form of seeds within the body of God as the Universe. In a predetermined manner (note 'Destiny') receiving favorable time-space, environment-condition, the seed once germinated.

Just as there are various types of parasites, insects, vermin, fungi etc., in our body, somewhat so the position of primitive organisms and primitive plants in God's body. Primitive organisms and primitive plants like microbes and fungi etc. are also important parts of God's body.

Their life-cycle, their course of action, birth-death, procreation, etc. are caught under the special observation of the child-God. Watching their activities with deep interest and attention, various thoughts, ideas and imaginations began to emerge in the mind of the child-God. Gradually it got addicted to childish games. The researcher-artist-mind wakes up in the pursuit of creation.

God up to its youth — at different stages of development, at different degrees of its mental states and powers, based on the concept of this born-spontaneously primordial organism and primordial plant, with the different colors of imaginations of its mind, with different levels of consciousness and its body materials, in the laboratory-cum-studio of its body, it has created different types of organisms and plants one after another. If not as required - broke them, built them again. It

spent its childhood— adolescence, and much of its youth— addicted with creation.

The Creator (universe/God) is able to find out in detail – the S-Existence (another experience of everything) of the primitive creatures and primitive plants behind their physical forms. Then on a deeper and more thorough search, he eventually discovers the 'programming language language' by which this 'S-Existence' (Discussed about it later.) is created. Manifestations of various forms of 'S-Existence' are the entire universe including living beings and plants.

Subsequently, through many experiments and researches with that 'programming language language', it gradually started creating new organisms and plants one after another.

At the beginning of creation - this man of today was beyond its (infant and adolescent God-mind's) imagination. However, it was deep in the consciousness ~ it was dormant in the form of seeds. The creation of so many types of animals and plants would never have been possible by God, if it had not seen the original animals and plants. All this could not be imagined. But they are the basis behind the creation of these numerous types of strange-looking creatures and plants. The 'idea' came from there.

Creation has progressed one after the other through successive stages of development through experiments. However, not all forms and ideas of creation come from the God-Mind. Many things have been created involuntarily and accidentally while creating.

This is the case also with us too, many times while experimenting, while building many things, amazing things are created. Which are not intentional creation.

It happens to God as it does to us. Then, if the God-mind approves — it remains, otherwise it is broken again. This breaking and making happened more in God's young age. In adulthood, such incidence is much less.

This change in the organism—this metamorphosis—does not happen equally in all places—at all times—in all cases. Depending on the time-place, environmental conditions and the physical and mental condition of that organism, different degrees of change can occur in different organisms. Again, organisms resulting from sexual intercourse between organisms of different species that have varied to different degrees and in different types in different places may have different shapes and different behaviors.

In this way, increasing variation also results in biodiversity. As humans are no longer confined to one place and within the same human group, this change has been greatest in humans. At present, most people have become a very hybrid race as a result of the aforementioned changes and admixtures.

Apart from God's voluntary role in the creation of so much diversity on earth, there is the involuntary role of the world system in the internal modification of organisms for the sake of adaptation to the environment, and sexual interbreeding.

As in any creative act, at various stages of creation, God had to face various obstacles. And it had to solve them and move on. But not all obstacles~ all problems have been overcome. Sometimes by removing obstacles ~ sometimes by digging or bypassing them, sometimes by surrendering, sometimes by accepting its influence~ dominance, it moved forward.

One thing to note here is that if you think of God as omniscient from the beginning of creation, you will be wrong. Its consciousness also increased gradually, step by step~ from very childhood along the path

of development. Along with the growth of consciousness, its creations are also impressed by the improved mind and consciousness. Its creation has gradually improved. Uts creativity has increased in excellence.

Later, God in its keen observation noticed one thing, many of the creatures it created were not able to adapt themselves to the changed environment. Not being able to sustain their existence.

Then, during the creation of the next organisms, it incorporated some 'program' into their cells so that they would be able to adapt themselves little by little to the changing environment. It was not possible to do this technique with all the creatures that were created earlier. This is a much higher level of creation art than today's genetic engineering. Which maybe people will be able to discover sometime in the future.

The changes an organism makes in itself through its internal programming are mainly adaptive— behavioral changes. In this case, although there are minor external changes, the internal changes are the main ones here. And, as a result of the change in mentality, the change that occurs in the appearance and expression, in this case only that changes. Major physical changes do not occur in that case. All the great changes we notice are God-made.

There is an imprint of the Creator's intelligence in various worldly creations. This can be clearly understood by a little inquisitive inquiry. And if you follow the intelligence, you will find the intelligent creator. In many traditional religious views — God is omniscient! In reality, it is not, little by little through action and enjoyment ~ through the acquisition of knowledge and experience, his mental development has happened and is still happening.

It must be remembered that the creator started creation with its child-consciousness based on that original living cell. Little by little, as its knowledge, experience and consciousness grew, its creations

developed at a very slow pace. Various events happened on the way of creation, breaking and building many times, overcoming many obstacles, long-term research and tireless efforts as a result of the need to create living beings with advanced consciousness, at one time the creation of humans became possible.

God's creations are similar to a great extent to our creation of animated characters, video games on our computers, holograms and robots.

fig- 5

Among all the motives which have been active at different times behind the creation of various creatures and plants, chief are — the fun of play, the joy of creation, renovating itself and its playhouse, and enjoying the wonder of new discoveries, Eliminating loneliness, adding variety to life by removing the monotony of life, and satisfying lust in

different ways. And, besides that, there is the purpose with which the Original Being started this activity.

Although God had a largely direct role behind its created beings and their way of life in the beginning, Later its interest gradually waned. After God reaches its maturity, it has no further role in these matters. It didn't even have the role of a spectator when it becomes old enough. After starting once According to the pre-ordained worldly system, the creation is going on with extreme negligence.

After creating human beings with somewhat high consciousness, God gradually gave up these puppet games and engaged in introspective self-searching as it gained progressively higher consciousness in the second half of its youth. It becomes anxious to know its identity. At the same time, in search of its friend, it became eager to meet it. Creation continues on its own way. It no longer has the time—the will—the mental state to look at them.

God, at the end of its creation, created the higher conscious being—man on earth and other forms of conscious existence elsewhere, in the light of its higher consciousness and pre-acquired knowledge and experience. On the earth this man is to a large extent like its child. This man will gradually develop and pass through the various higher levels of consciousness—through progression, eventually arriving at its level of consciousness—and meet it. This is one of the desires of God behind the creation of man. It has created or 'programmed' the human mind in that way.

In the beginning the relationship between the creation and the creator was like that of a toy doll and its player. Later, somewhat like a master and his pet. There the creature does not know its creator properly, does not know it well. They do not have the knowledge and consciousness to know the Creator. Its relationship with human beings is like that of child and birth parent. This man will know the Creator

one day. Man can gradually rise to the mental level of the Creator, ~the result of this desire is~ Man.

But human beings are not really the children of the universe or God. But like the children. Although human beings are created from the body and mind of God, they are not the children of Vishwatma (God). To be the children they must— in all respects—be like the whole body and mind of God. Which will gradually develop from the infant through a certain process and will eventually acquire the form-qualities-powers of God. Although the full form of God is symbolically present in them latently, because of the method of construction, and because they reside within the body of God, it will never be awakened, never fully developed. But human beings are not really the children of the universe or God. But like the children. Although human beings are created from the body and mind of God, they are not the children of Vishwatma (God). To be the children they must— in all respects—be like the whole body and mind of God. Which will gradually develop from the infant through a certain process and will eventually acquire the form-qualities-powers of God. Although the full form of God is symbolically present in them latently, because of the method of construction, and because they reside within the body of God, it will never be awakened, it will never get a chance to develop.

On earth, only God's best creation is man with some exceptions. Man is the product of God's youth, ~the last creation. So far God has become a lot mature, along with his creation has also improved a lot. In course of time, despite the beginning of filial piety in God, as there was no opportunity to create children, it had to make up for that lack by creating human beings. In that sense, man is not merely a toy doll or a mere work of art created by God. Much like children.

God has created human beings in such a way that they can progress and develop step by step, and attain its reach at one time. While there is no possibility of becoming God as an individual universe, there is

the possibility of one day reaching the God-conscious level, of union with God.

Just as God possesses multiple minds and several inactive or latent minds at every level of consciousness except the first stage of creation, so also the various beings created by God at different levels of consciousness possess multiple minds. Although their level of consciousness is much lower than God's level of consciousness at creation, yet because they are made of God's body-mind and consciousness, their mental makeup is somewhat similar to God's lower level of consciousness.

Creatures of the lowest level of consciousness also have a mind, but a very low level of mind. Like very basic computers created long before advanced computers or various devices like calculator.

Through evolution Reptiles did not evolve into animals, animals did not evolve into primitive humans, and primitive humans evolved into conscious humans. Each particular class of living being is created by Vishwatma or God. As 2 or 3 minds or consciousness-levels exist in each organism, and also because there are many similarities in body and mind characteristics between two closely related organisms, and as organisms of the next level show some improvement from those of the previous level, naturally, it may seem that they have originated through evolution.

But it is not. An organism has not evolved into or transformed into the next higher conscious level of organism. As God's knowledge and experience grew, it constantly acquired new ideas, and consequently it was able to create increasingly advanced creatures. So each particular class of living being is created by Vishwatma or God. Vishwatma (God) has at many times created another type of organism by making some changes on the mold or model of a previously created organism of a particular nature.

It was impossible for God to imagine the creation of today's advanced beings~ humans and other higher conscious entity~ at the beginning of the creation~ at the level of its low-consciousness level.

These human beings and other sentient beings have come into existence through the constant seeking, breaking, experimenting, and creating new things along the path of consciousness development—the gradual growth of knowledge and experience and the development of consciousness.

According to this theory of creation, God in the form of the universe created the plants and animals . Yes, they are created by God's will. But, it is not as if one after another new plants and animals were created as it wished like a freak. Behind all these new creations there is a long time of continuous research and artistic thinking.

Here, the God-mind gradually develops. God's knowledge-experience and consciousness developed as it progressed. Along with that, its creation has also been developed. Little by little it perfected its creation. As a result, there will be signs or evidence of progress between yesterday's creation and today's creation, it is normal.

Creation itself evolved little by little in very few cases. Whatever happened, happened by God's will. This is made possible by God embedding that necessary instruction (in program form) into its creation.

We are all moving towards that one goal~ some knowingly, some unknowingly. So some know, some don't know~ actually we are travelers on the same path. Unremitting movement through action and enjoyment, from unbloomed consciousness to full blown consciousness. No one stops here, does not stop. Variation in speed based on level of consciousness due to environment and many other factors. Some are ahead, some are behind.

Although this world appears to be divided into fragments, the universe or God is not many. It is the only one. If you observe a little better, you will understand that God has not even a void in it as far as it has expanded so far. Everywhere in the universe is filled with either matter or some energy—particles, primordials, or other matter unknown to us—other energy. The sense of multiplicity is only in our less conscious mind. Ever since the beginning of creation, the universe has been expanding, ~there has never been a 'Many'.

As if, in a pot of water~ many small - large ice cubes. Each particle—each water droplet— simply because of ignorance thinking of itself as a separate entity. This is how illusory multiplicity is created.

In this context, cosmic time has also been created~ with the creation of the universe. Cosmic time and the time of original being are not the same. As is not the same—our earthly time. Before the birth of the cosmos, before the creation of cosmic time~ there was only time of original entity or primeval time. I have discussed in detail about 'Time' in another chapter.

fig- 6

Moving forward to the end~

Seeking pleasure, engaging in action, knowledge is gained without seeking it. However, if one does not want to get pleasure, if one does not move forward knowing that one will have to suffer, therefore, intense hungers are always burning in this body and mind. Along with that, there is pain and suffering, the urge to protect oneself, to escape from them one has to run. While extinguishing these irritations, more irritations increase, knowledge and consciousness increases without knowing.

Driven by their impulse, there comes a time when one feels joy in gaining knowledge. Gradually self-knowledge, self-consciousness, the underlying latent self-power develops. Then at some point when this mind develops into God Consciousness, then with perfection comes deadlock. After assuming one form, separation is no longer possible. A sense of oneness with God ~ immediately comes the call to merge~ become one.

Finally, as soon as the Vishwatma or God-mind is fully developed, all its parts— even the unconscious-dark part—come to full development at lightning speed. The ignorance-blindness-darkness of all its parts is removed and became luminous in an instant.

At the same time, it is seen that the two opposite worlds have gradually expanded and come closer to each other in the desire for union. Not only our world, but the same thing happens in other worlds as well.

Suddenly, with a flash of bright light, everything disappeared like a jugglery! The union of opposite worlds brings about the end of creation. This happens not only in our world and its opposite world,

but at the same time, this same thing happens in all other worlds and their opposite worlds.

After watching a very exciting play, the exhausted original being 'Paramatma' surrendered itself to the lap of deep sleep.

The chapter 'Unveiling the Mystery of Creation' ends here. That which is difficult to know, even if known, is difficult to express, that unexpressed Original being 'Paramatma' is possible to express very little ~ only by its will. We have to be satisfied with this for now.

As the two opposite universes gradually expand and come into contact with each other, both universes disappear.

fig- 7

Some evidence of God's mind and intelligence

The intelligence of the Creator is evident in the strategies devised by the Creator to maintain the existence and lineage of mortal beings through reproduction. And, intelligence is the sign of the presence of 'Mind'. That is, where there is intelligence, there must be mind.

Now let's talk about that strategy, the strategy of arranging sexual pleasure in the organism and enticing the organism towards sexual pleasure, by embedding the command of sexual intercourse in it through 'programming language', the technique of motivating or forcing the organism to have sexual intercourse is definitely a sign of God's intelligence.

Another sign of the Creator's intelligence is the creation of male and female organisms for the purpose of creating superior beings, and providing them with suitable bodies, minds and genital organs. Behind all these there is obviously the existence of intelligence or intelligent conscious mind.

Besides, so that we don't destroy our bodies, we try to escape from diseases, injuries, attacks, the Creator has given us the feeling of pain and the urge to protect ourselves.

Although, not all of its works are complete and flawless, not satisfactory enough to many of us, yet it has done much with its knowledge and consciousness during creation (at a particular level of development of consciousness). God has also given us many self-defense systems.

If you search, you will find many more such proofs. And if you observe a little carefully, it will be seen that it has created various techniques to make us from low conscious humans to higher conscious human beings.

Also, a closer look reveals that the God-mind has been developing bit by bit over a long period of time. The improvement of its creative power along with the development of mind can be clearly understood by looking at its progressive (starting from insect to advanced man) creation.

Conclusion:

It will go back to where it started. In the middle, various dramatic Illusory events of happiness and sadness, laughter and tears are happening like a colorful dream.

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What exactly Destiny is: an exploration from a scientific viewpoint
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**UNVEILING THE TRUTH OF 'TIME' AND 'TIME TRAVEL'
ALONG THE PATH OF SCIENCE!**

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<http://www.ijrpr.com/v2i9.php>

**'S-Existence : There is Another Existence of Everything' 06 Dec 21 in
Global Journal of Science Frontier Research (U.S.) GJSFR-A Volume
21 Issue 4 Version 1.0 PDF link below:**
https://globaljournals.org/GJSFR_Volume21/2-S-Existence-There-is-Another.pdf

Author's profile:

Sumeru Ray alias Maharshi MahaManas : The greatest sage of the time

Maharshi MahaManas being sympathetic to the suffering of the helpless troubled human he has worked tirelessly all his life to alleviate their misery and poverty.

He understood from his deep thinking and experience that the root cause of most of the problems and mishaps caused by human beings is lack of adequate knowledge and consciousness and illness of body and mind. Most problems will be solved if the human mind develops enough. That is why he has created an excellent and incomparable mind-development education system, its name is 'MahaManan' education.

If we can implement his multifaceted revolutionary work and thought, then there will surely be a radical change in human life. All that is needed for this is a strong team dedicated to the cause of real human development in the path shown by him.

He did not look at all our problems from above or from the surface. He has found the root cause of the problem and discovered the way to its real solution.

He is truly a free-spirited science-minded man. He did not try to find solution by flying in the sky with the wings of imagination. His every thought has moved forward along the path of reasoning~ judgment and reality.

It would not be an exaggeration to call him the great sage of the modern times who sees the truth. He has made many scientific discoveries in his search for the truth of life and cosmic life.

It was not at all happy for him to continue his exploration for truth. He did not think of his own happiness and prosperity, but he had to endure a lot of hardships and obstacles for the welfare of human beings and went ahead tirelessly in search of the way of real liberation of the human beings. This is how the great doctrine of this time~ 'MahaVad' (Mahaism) was born.

Maharshi MahaManas is a free-minded rational sage of this millennium, master of reasonable spirituality, a multi-talented creator, researcher, writer, philosopher, awakener, educator, multifaceted free thinker and he is self-dedicated to real human improvement.

He is the creator of the great doctrine of the time 'MahaVad' (Mahaism) and the founder of an epoch-making new religion called 'MahaDharma' for real human development including true mind development.

He has extensive knowledge in fine arts, literature, meditation, yoga, healing arts, self-development programs, lyric, story and screenwriting, music composition and filmmaking, newspaper and magazine editing. If you are interested to know more about him, you should read his books. It will also be possible to know a lot about him by searching the internet.

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